

ACCESSIBILITY EVALUATION QUESTIONNAIRE

1. Were the information accessible?

- Strongly Disagree
- Disagree
- Neutral
- Agree
- Strongly Agree

2. In your opinion, how were the image descriptions?

- Very Poor
- Poor
- Fair
- Good
- Very Good
- Not Applicable

3. In your opinion, how were the icon descriptions?

- Very Poor
- Poor
- Fair
- Good
- Very Good

4. In your opinion, how were the button descriptions?

- Very Poor
- Poor
- Fair
- Good
- Very Good

5. Are the links described clearly and suggestive of their content?

- Strongly Disagree
- Disagree
- Neutral
- Agree
- Strongly Agree

6. What did you think of the shortcuts?

- Extremely Insufficient
- Insufficient
- Fair
- Sufficient
- Extremely Sufficient

7. Do you find the information you need?

- Very Easily
- Easily
- With Some Difficulty \
- With Extreme Difficulty
- I Can't Find

8. Do you identify with the adopted textual language?

- Strongly Disagree
- Disagree
- Neutral
- Agree
- Strongly Agree

If the answer is negative, please provide comments.

9. Did you face any difficulty identifying any interface element? If yes, please provide a brief description.

10. Did you encounter any navigation difficulties?

- No Yes

If the answer is yes, what were the difficulties encountered? Please specify.

11. Provide a brief overview of your impressions regarding iVProg4All. You can highlight successes and suggest improvements if applicable

References

Franco, R.P., 2018. Audiodescrição Em Objetos De Aprendizagem Na Plataforma Ead Dell Accessible Learning. Master's thesis. Universidade Estadual do Ceará. Fortaleza-CE.